

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS AND CONDITIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF THE PROFESSIONAL WORLDVIEW OF SCHOOLCHILDREN

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***Abstract.** This article discusses the issues of the formation and development of the professional worldview in the career guidance of young students in general education schools as well as ideas on pedagogical conditions. This article describes the ideas of secondary schools about the pedagogical conditions and the basics of the formation and development of their worldview in the process of professional orientation of students.*

***Keywords:** profession, professional worldview, career orientation, youth, career, vision concepts, polytechnical education, scientific worldview, vocational education.*

Today, the training of highly qualified specialists corresponding to international standards is tightly connected with the provision of thorough professional-oriented education in secondary schools, the sustainable development of overall education. At the same time, this requires organizing the educational process on the basis of professional knowledge. This leads to the need to organize the educational process taking into account the requirements of the market economy, introduce relevant teaching technologies, and improve methodological support aimed at constantly updating the content of education. In continuity with modern teaching technologies, it is relevant because it is aimed at developing a professional worldview, which is considered an important component of educating mature person and harmonious personality, and researching it from a pedagogical point of view, and taking it to a new level.

In the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, one of the priority tasks is “to further improve the system of continuing education, increase the capacity of quality education services, continue the policy of training highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market”[1]. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out scientific and practical research on improving and practical implementation of the current methods and tools for the formation and development of professional worldview in students of secondary schools.

This research work serves to a certain extent in ensuring the implementation of the tasks defined in the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5313 dated January 25, 2018 “On measures for the fundamental improvement of the general secondary, secondary special and vocational education system” and PF-5712 dated April 29, 2019 “On the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”, as well as, the Decree No. 3931 dated September 5, 2018 “On measures to introduce new principles of management into the public education system”, and the Decree No. PF-27 dated February 28, 2023 “On implementation of the New Uzbekistan development strategy aimed at 2022-2026 in the “Year of caring for people and quality education” and other regulatory legal documents.

The concept of worldview. Each person has their own vision of the world, views and conclusions about self and others, life and the universe. These visions, concepts, views and conclusions determine the meaning of the attitude of a particular person to other people and their daily activities. In this sense, worldview is a system of views, visions, knowledge about reality that surrounds a person, the point and structure of the world, their place in it. Worldview is imagining, perceiving and knowing the world in the most general way.

In order to make a worthy contribution to the implementation of these tasks, research work was carried out on the formation of a professional worldview based on knowledge of chemistry in secondary schools.

Literature review. An analysis of pedagogical literature shows that the question of professional orientation of students in Uzbekistan was discussed by Bakieva, the topic of pedagogical conditions for the orientation of students to the profession by S.Saiytov. O.A.Smanbaev researched on the pedagogical foundations for the preparation of students of rural schools to consciously choose a profession in livestock while A.Khaitov studied the issue of preparing students of rural schools for labor activities on the basis of general polytechnical and professional education.

M.Rakhmatullaeva explored the question of the formation of a worldview in students along with philosophical-social analysis of the importance of the process of forming a scientific worldview in young people; A.P.Babotaev pedagogically defined the formation of a scientific worldview in secondary schools., A.K.Turashbekov emphasized the importance of the scientific worldview, R.Kh.Djuraev studied the formation of dialectical and materialistic worldview in the person, M.P.Mukhamedjanova learned the questions of formation of scientific worldview in upper-class students on the basis of school and family cooperation;, A.Khatamov studied the problems of raising worldview and cognitive activity of the individual.[2]

Professional worldview is a system of worldviews, which is the basis of a holistic thinking about systemic factors, social values of a particular profession, professions in general. The leading strategy for modernizing vocational education has become the orientation of the potential and resources of the vocational school to the formation of a future specialist as a person capable of self-determination, self-education, self-expression, with general cultural and professional competencies. These skills in total determine the formation and development of the professional worldview as a system of professional ideals, the intellectual and value-emotional attitude of the individual to professional activity, lifelong readiness for study, the ability to self-organize and competitiveness in the labor market. The awareness of a graduate of a general secondary school about belongingness to a certain professional community, the ability to create professional activity programs are one of the subjective factors of the development of the modern economy. This forces the vocational education system to solve qualitatively new tasks and mediates a new approach to the process of forming a professional worldview among students of general education organizations.

The analysis of the literature on the topic showed that a number of studies are devoted to the problems of forming a professional worldview. Pedagogical scientists working in the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States expressed their opinion on the formation of a professional worldview of school students in their research works.

Theoretical foundations of vocational education were reflected in the research works of S.Y.Batishev, E.F.Zeer, B.S.Lednev, G.V.Mukhametjanova, P.F.Kubrushko, A.M.Novikov,

V.A.Camelina, N.B.Pugacheva, G.M.Romantsev, I.P.Smirnov, E.V.Tkachenko and others. Reflected in the research of et al. Laws and characteristics of the formation of the future specialists were reviewed by N.S.Glukhanyuk, G.N.Zhukov, A.B.Kaganov, V.A.Calney, E.A.Klimov, A.K.Markova, M.I.Rojhkov, V.D.Shadrikov and others. N.E.Kasatkina, E.A.Klimov, L.M.Mitina studied the theoretical foundations of professional self-determination. Various approaches to the understanding of professional self-awareness were discussed in the works of V.D.Bragina, S.A.Dneprov, A.K.Markova, L.M.Mitina, P.A.Shavir -Cited . The problem of the formation of professional interest among future specialists were researched by G.H.Aisina, H.A.Baksheva, A.A.Verbitskiy. [3].

Results and discussion. Professional orientation of students, effective formation of their professional worldview, socio-professional relations, psychological qualities that require professional growth are of utmost importance, which include:

- personal needs, life goals, tasks, requirements, interests, content of relationships organized with the participation of a person, value orientations, psychological position;
- self-assessment in terms of professional interests, requirements, professional competence;
- mental state and emotional image;
- relations to the process of labor organization;
- psychological knowledge of labor and profession;
- professional ability, professional potential and opportunities for professional growth;
- opportunities to enrich profession-specific experience, including creative thinking;
- professional growth planning;
- psychological conflicts (mental qualities that are completely or to a certain extent incompatible with professional activity, in this case it is appropriate to identify operational conflicts specific to the profession);
- areas of professional growth.

Scientific worldview is formed on the basis of continuous and consistent acquisition by human knowledge, thorough assimilation of existing knowledge and the life experience. The formation of a person's worldview is considered a long-term, dynamic process.

Also, the worldview is divided into certain types such as:

Mythological worldview is a worldview that represents a complex of imaginations formed on the basis of figurative perception of existence in the primitive community system. The concept of "mythology itself (from Greek "mythos" – myth, tale, narrative, "logos" – "science", "doctrine") means tales belonging to a group of people.

Religious worldview is a set of ideas, traditions and rituals that represent the acceptance of existence on the basis of belief in divine power, in God. Translated from Arabic, the concept of "religion" means "faith", belief".

Socio-political worldview is a generalized system of people's political views on objectively existing political life and their attitude towards political activity.

Philosophical worldview (from Greek "philosophy". "φιλία" – "love", "aspiration", "passion", "σοφία" – "wisdom"; "φιλοσοφία" – "striving for wisdom") is a worldview based on the theoretical acceptance of natural and social existence, the philosophical attitude of a person towards existence.

Aesthetic worldview is a worldview based on an approach to natural and social existence based on aesthetic values such as beauty, ugliness, funny, tragedy, etc. [2].

The opportunities for the formation of a professional polytechnical thinking skills in practical training in technology science, first of all, its effectiveness component increases in the process of studying each topic of the lesson, which makes the professional polytechnical thinking skills very important.

Also, opportunities are expanded for the formation of practical activities in practical classes of technology, with the help of which professional polytechnical thinking skills are carried out. The necessity of developing these actions does not allow to fully computerize the performance of their practical work. In order to form the creative organizer of the professional polytechnical thinking skills, it is necessary that assignments for practical work should encourage students to make things with their own hands, which allows them to develop mental actions to put forward hypotheses and verify that they are correct.

Conclusions and suggestions. In the process of technology training, students are brought up with a sense of preservation of equipment in the workshop, economical use of raw materials. The labor culture in training workshops, organization of the workplace, proper planning of training and work activities; the use of various devices along with hand tools in the lessons of Technology and vocational education is also of great importance, since they not only improve the quality of work of students, but also increase labor productivity at the same time. The teacher's personal example during the demonstration of work and labor methods is considered as a powerful educational tool for students. In revealing the content of the topic in the process of practical training in technology and vocational education, the goals, objectives of the labor, work and vocational education are realized and a professional worldview is formed [4].

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".// Collection of legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - T., 2017. B.39.
2. M.Sh.Islamova. "Formation of the professional worldview of students". Monograph. Tashkent, Chirchik, 2020.
3. T.S.Turkina. "Формирование профессионального мировоззрения у студентов учреждений среднего профессионального образования". Thesis.
4. Kh.Nabieva. "Organizing "Technology" lessons in secondary schools". Zamonaviy ta'lim. 2018.